

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group

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Science (Cefas)

Detecting marine slicks from
shipwrecks using satellite
observation data

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1 Executive Summary

Thousands of shipwrecks around the world still contain oil and fuel from past conflicts and maritime accidents, slowly releasing hydrocarbons into the sea as their hulls corrode. These wrecks pose a long-term hazard to marine ecosystems and coastal communities, threatening fisheries, food security, and biodiversity. Globally, it is estimated that between 2.5 and 20 million tonnes of petroleum products remain trapped in submerged vessels. Detecting and monitoring these leaks is essential for environmental protection, yet it remains difficult at scale. Most satellite-based monitoring relies on visual interpretation or single-image classifiers that struggle under variable lighting, sea states, and weather conditions. Developing automated, reliable detection methods that can operate under these real-world constraints is critical for enabling continuous, large-scale observation of shipwreck pollution.

The objective of this Data Study Group (DSG) challenge was to develop and demonstrate automated methods for detecting oil slicks from shipwrecks using satellite imagery provided by the Centre for Environment, Fisheries and Aquaculture Science (Cefas). The dataset comprised time series of Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) and Sentinel-2 multispectral optical images (MSI) collected over nineteen known wreck sites between 2014 and 2025. Each site was centred on a geo-referenced wreck location and accompanied by delineated slick masks and environmental metadata, including wind speed, wave height, temperature, and seismic activity. Together, these data provided a unique opportunity to test how machine-learning models can combine radar, optical, and physical information to improve the detection and interpretation of slicks under realistic environmental variability.

This DSG demonstrated practical advances in automated slick detection using SAR, optical, and environmental datasets. A foveated downsampling method, which preserves full resolution near the image centre while progressively reducing resolution with distance from the wreck location, reduced SAR inputs by a factor of 81 while preserving fine detail around wreck centres and stabilising training at fixed input sizes. For Sentinel-2 MSI, spectral analysis identified strong inter-band correlations and led to composite indices that improved contrast between oil films and open water. The Oil Spill Index and two RGB composites highlighted spectral flattening and emulsification patterns, which informed model inputs and band selection.

Model comparisons showed the advantage of temporal context and multi-sensor learning. Vision Transformers (ViTs) consistently outperformed Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) when short image sequences were used, with Area Under Receiver Operating Curve (AUROC) and average precision metrics improving over single-image classification. Bilinear fusion of SAR and MSI data with gating achieved a large performance gain, increasing validation accuracy from 0.81 to 0.938.

Logistic regression and Random Forest models linked slick occurrence to calmer conditions, and class-balanced sampling improved sensitivity and AUROC. Grouped K-fold validation, in which entire wreck sites were held out, demonstrated that random splits can inflate accuracy and confirmed the need for spatially independent evaluation. A physics-informed neural network (PINN) framework was also outlined to couple advection–diffusion dynamics with machine-learning outputs once concentration estimates become available.

Segmentation benchmarks confirmed the difficulty of pixel-level slick delineation under severe class imbalance. Across 36 configurations, patch-based processing achieved slightly higher accuracy than global resizing, but slick-class IoU and F1 remained low, showing that model architecture alone cannot overcome sparse positive labels.

The outcomes of this DSG establish a framework for detecting marine slicks from satellite imagery that is both computationally efficient and methodologically robust. The introduction of foveated downsampling enables a substantial reduction in SAR data volume while retaining spatial detail in regions of interest, supporting applications across large image collections. Detection performance is improved through the integration of SAR and MSI data under variable conditions, while the use of short temporal sequences provides greater consistency than single-image approaches. The incorporation of environmental covariates further aids interpretation by relating observed slick patterns to external drivers.

2 Introduction

Worldwide, there are approximately 8,500 known shipwrecks that are potential sources of pollution, primarily from hydrocarbons such as fuels, lubricating oils, and hydraulic fluids, affecting marine and coastal environments. Those wrecks which have been submerged for long periods of time pose a greater risk of producing contaminant slicks as they corrode or are dismantled by illegal salvage operations. The release of pollutants contaminates marine ecosystems and shorelines, threatening the livelihoods, food security, and culture of local communities. Globally, an estimated 2.5 million to 20 million tonnes of oil and petroleum distillate fuels remain stored in submerged wrecks, a figure that reflects both the scale of the problem and the uncertainty surrounding it.

The use of satellite imagery for detecting and tracking marine oil slicks has increased significantly in recent years, particularly Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) and multi-band, high-resolution optical Multispectral Imaging (MSI). SAR is considered an effective technology for mapping and monitoring due to its independence from weather conditions, illumination, and time of day. MSI by contrast, capture frequency bands that can reveal features such as surface sheen, discolouration, and emulsification patterns associated with hydrocarbon presence, and typically offer shorter orbital revisit intervals than SAR sensors.

This study explores the problem of slick detection from shipwrecks using real-world satellite time series. Working with SAR and optical imagery, delineated slick masks, physical covariates, and known source locations, participants will develop models to segment and characterise hydrocarbon leakage over time. The task supports experimentation with sensor fusion, spatio-temporal learning, physical priors, and uncertainty-aware modelling aimed at improving accuracy, interpretability, and generalisability.

2.1 DSG Objectives

This challenge is focused on time series analysis and prediction, using computer vision datasets. Imagery for this challenge is drawn from the European Space Agency's Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 constellations, providing SAR and MSI data as complementary all-weather radar and multispectral observations over the wreck sites. The detection of slicks using satellite imagery has traditionally relied on single-image classification or heuristic filtering methods. While these approaches

can identify clear slicks under controlled conditions, they often struggle with false positives, inconsistent performance across sites, and a lack of temporal reasoning. Very few published methods attempt multi-modal fusion with optical imagery or account for physical drivers such as wind or sea temperature. This presents a gap, and an opportunity for participants to explore AI/ML methods for segmentation, time series analysis and modelling, uncertainty quantification, and environmental conditioning in this still underdeveloped area of research, focusing on the use of the Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 imagery for:

- Improvement of oil slick detection using SAR and Optical MSI imagery
- Enhancement of detection robustness and generalisation by incorporating environmental covariates such as wind, waves, and temperature
- Exploration of SAR–optical fusion for uncertainty-aware classification and detection
- Compression of high-capacity detection and forecasting models into lightweight versions for scalable, real-time deployment without loss of reliability

This study aims to achieve progress towards scalable and cloud-compatible prototypes that use AI/ML to improve and expand the capability to detect and predict the behaviour of potential slicks produced by sunken ships on satellite SAR/optical/MSI images. The overarching goal is the automation and improvement of detectability of slicks originating from actively leaking shipwrecks and the forward prediction of slick behaviour based on historical patterns and physical covariates.

3 Data Overview

3.1 Dataset Description

The dataset for this project consisted of 19 shipwreck sites, with a total of 12,218 SAR and 6,924 MSI captured across all 19 sites between 2014 and 2025, each centred the known, georeferenced wreck locations. All images in the dataset had already undergone denoising and correction of incidence angle, as both SAR and MSI imagery are affected by sensor and environmental noise, and measured signal intensity varies with satellite acquisition geometry.

Slick delineation rasters were provided and were created by Cefas, classifying each image pixel as land, sea surface, or potential slick. A representative compilation of slick delineations for USS ATLANTA, located in the Solomon Islands, is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Slick delineations for 2015-2024 from the USS ATLANTA wreck site, near Honiara, one of the Solomon Islands in the south Pacific Ocean.

All SAR and MSI images had a pixel resolution of 2250×2250. The SAR imagery (Sentinel-1) was provided in two polarities, VV and VH, defined by the orientation of the satellite’s radar antenna during signal transmission and reception. VV denotes vertically transmitted and vertically received radar signals, and VH denotes vertically transmitted and horizontally received signals; these measure the strength of radar backscatter, which responds differently to surface roughness and geometry, offering complementary information about the sea surface. The MSI imagery (Sentinel-2) was provided with 12 spectral bands, spanning the visible, near-infrared, and shortwave infrared ranges, enabling discrimination between oil slicks, open water, and land based on distinct spectral signatures. Of the total images,

413 included annotated segmentation masks used for training and evaluation. The dataset exhibited extreme class imbalance, with approximately 2.1 billion background pixels (Class 0), 0.02 billion oil slick pixels (Class 1), and 0.3 billion land pixels (Class 2), corresponding to only 0.08 % of annotated pixels representing slicks.

Class	Pixel Count (billions)	Proportion (%)
Background (Class 0)	2.10	87.45
Land (Class 2)	0.30	12.47
Oil Slick (Class 1)	0.02	0.08

Table 1: Pixel-level class distribution across the 413 annotated Sentinel-2 MSI images. Oil slick pixels represent just 0.08 % of the total annotated pixels, reflecting the significant class imbalance inherent to operational oil spill detection.

Metadata for this study was used in addition to SAR and MSI datasets, which included information from Sentinel satellite observations presented in 94 columns. Key columns included the shipwreck identifier, latitude and longitude of the observation, acquisition date, and whether an oil slick was detected in the associated MSI/SAR image. Additional metadata included identifiers for the satellite pass identifier, granule id, and the spacecraft name. Furthermore, optical metadata also included image quality and sensor characteristics, such as cloudy pixel percentage, degraded MSI data percentage, radiometric quality, and solar irradiance.

Physical covariate data included weather data: wind speed, significant wave height, sea and air temperature acquired from the ERA5, which is a global atmospheric reanalysis dataset produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) and distributed via the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS). Seismic data from the U.S. Geological Survey’s Comprehensive Earthquake Catalogue (COMCAT), which provided earthquake event data including epicentre latitude and longitude, depth of quake origin, magnitude, magnitude type, date, time and distance from the wreck site to the reporting seismic station.

4 Data Exploration and Quality

4.1 Temporal Coverage and Volume

Figure 2 shows the monthly distribution of image acquisition across the complete time range. Coverage increases substantially from 2017 onward, peaking in mid-2018 through 2021. This reflects the operational maturity of both S1 and S2 missions. However, availability drops off slightly post-2022 due to the failure of one of the Sentinel-1 satellites that can be seen in Figure 3, and no data are recorded after the 1st of June 2025. Over 80% of Sentinel 1 and 2 inter-visit intervals are within one day, supporting the use of near-synchronous pairs (e.g., S1–S2) for multi-modal fusion or cross-validation design. The dense revisit frequency highlights combining both for time-sensitive monitoring.

Figure 2: Calendar heatmap of all available images from 2015–2025. Each cell shows the number of images per month per year.

Figure 3: Yearly image counts stratified by sensor (S1 and S2). S1 consistently contributes a higher volume.

4.2 Class Balance Exploration

As shown in Figure 4, the distribution of the ‘Slick Detected’ variable in the dataset is highly imbalanced. Out of 6,924 MSI observations used in this study, 6,457 belong to the class “Slick Undetected,” while only 467 are labelled as “Slick Detected,” and of 12,218 SAR observations, 11,577 belonged to the class “Slick Undetected,” while only 641 were labelled as “Slick Detected”. This large discrepancy indicates that the presence of oil slicks is a relatively rare event in the dataset.

Such an unbalanced distribution may lead to biased predictions toward the majority class if not properly addressed, and it necessitates additional effort in terms of data preprocessing, sampling strategies, or model design to ensure reliable detection of the minority class.

Figure 4: Comparison of total images for each sensor and associated rasters, showing a strong imbalance, with the majority of observations labelled as “Slick Undetected” and a smaller proportion labelled as “Slick Detected.”

4.3 Weather Data Exploration

Weather data were examined over time in relation to the presence of slicks detected in Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 imagery. For each wreck site, all weather variables were standardised to a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. Seasonal patterns were evident in the representative case of ORP KUJAWIAK time-series data (Fig. 6a), which illustrates temperature measurements and significant wave height. The raw series were overlaid with seven-day rolling averages, and slick occurrences were annotated on the plots. No consistent weather behaviour was visually identifiable preceding slick events.

Extreme weather events were identified in the time series as values exceeding 1.96 standard deviations (the 95th percentile). An example of this is shown in Fig. 6b for high wind events at HMS CASSANDRA. Although extreme wind may act as a potential precursor to slick formation, confirming this relationship would require a more advanced modelling approach.

The number of extreme weather events and the number of detected oil slicks were calculated for each wreck. These counts were normalised by the total number of weather observations and satellite images, respectively, and compared using Pearson’s correlation coefficient. As shown in Fig. 5, a strong positive correlation was observed between the frequency of wind speeds exceeding the 95th percentile

and the number of slick detections.

Rolling windows of weather variables (wind speed and temperature) were constructed and aligned with oil slick detection labels to train an LSTM model for slick classification. The model was not examined further owing to the severe class imbalance in slick detections, which limited its reliability.

Standardised wind conditions for the 21 days preceding each slick detection were plotted, using the SS COIMBRA as an illustrative example of pre-slick wind dynamics. This analysis highlighted the potential value of incorporating detailed weather information into future slick classification models.

Figure 5: Correlation of the percentage of slick detections against extreme values (> 95th percentile) for MSI and wind measures for all wrecks.

Figure 6: Weather observations. **(a)** Average sea temperature (swt) and significant wave height (swh) for ORP KUJAWIAK (7-day rolling avg). Both trends are sinusoidal and offset, with highest swt during summer months, while swh peaks during the winter **(b)** Time series of average wind speed for HMS CASSANDRA (7-day rolling avg) and 'x' markers for extreme values ($> 95^{th}$ percentile.). Wind speed and extreme wind events are most frequent during winter seasons. In both **(a)** and **(b)**, slick detection is indicated with relation to the plotted parameters by vertical dashed red lines.

4.3.1 Weather Data Effects on Dataset

The influence of wave height and wind velocity, identified as the most significant variables in slick detection, was examined. Their effects were visualised using linear regression of wind speed through time, comparing corresponding binary slick states. Figure 7 shows that the regression trends differed in magnitude but gradually converged over time.

Figure 7: Linear regression for every wreck comparing wind speed with and without detected oil slick

To quantify the differences between the two states, a box plot was produced showing the mean, quartiles, and range of wind velocities measured in images labelled for each state. As shown in Figure 8, the distribution of wind speeds differed noticeably between slick and non-slick conditions.

Wind speed was selected as previous studies [9, 3, 5, 1] have consistently identified it as the dominant factor influencing slick detectability across multiple investigations.

Figure 8: A comparison of the spread of the frequency of data for images with and without oil slicks

The probability densities of slick and non-slick observations across different wind velocities were visualised. Figure 9 shows that slick occurrences were most frequent when wind speeds ranged between 0 and 7 m s⁻¹. Beyond this range, slick density declined sharply, falling below 0.01 above 10 m s⁻¹. In contrast, non-slick densities decreased more gradually and did not fall below 0.01 until around 17 m s⁻¹. This 70% higher threshold indicated a strong dependence of slick detection on wind velocity.

Figure 9: Histogram density plot for SAR images indicating the occurrences of Slick detection and No Slick detection with relation to wind speed. Slick detection is more common at low wind speed and demonstrates a rapid decrease at wind speeds between 7 and 10 m/s, and almost no detections at wind speeds exceeding 10 m/s. The No detection population demonstrates lower peak densities at low wind speeds and a more gradual reduction as wind speed increases.

4.4 Statistical Exploration of MSI Data

4.4.1 Spectral Band Correlations

To improve computational efficiency and reduce model complexity, spectral bands were evaluated to determine their relative contribution to slick detection. The analysis began with a correlation matrix, shown in Figure 10, assessing inter-band relationships to identify redundant or highly collinear spectral features.

Figure 10: Heatmap showing the correlation between spectral bands in MSI imagery.

The correlation matrix was generated to examine inter-band relationships and identify redundancies that could influence model performance. Pixel value distributions were further analysed across confirmed slicks, revealing that detectability varied between bands and across images.

To evaluate band combinations that enhance slick discrimination, several spectral indices and composite ratios were tested. A greyscale Oil Spill $((B3+B4)/B2)$ was designed to normalise brightness and glint effects, providing a more stable indicator for threshold-based detection. Two RGB composites were also constructed to visualise spectral contrasts associated with oil presence.

RGB Composite A combined the red-edge and shortwave infrared regions to capture oil-induced spectral flattening and surface emulsification:

$R=(B05+B06)/B07$, $G=(B03+B04)/B02$, $B=(B11+B12)/B08$, enhancing the distinction between oil films and background water while reducing illumination-related false positives.

RGB Composite B emphasised visible and red-edge contrasts using $R=B03/B02$, $G=(B03+B04)/B02$, and $B=(B06+B07)/B05$, enhancing the distinction between oil films and background water while reducing illumination-related false positives.

Figure 11: Comparison of spectral composite visualisations for slick detection

4.4.2 Cloud Cover

Cloud cover directly affects image quality and the reliability of surface classification. To assess its influence, the distribution of cloud coverage was compared between observations with and without detected slicks (Figure 12). The overall cloud fraction was similar across both classes, suggesting that atmospheric conditions did not systematically bias slick detection, though cloud presence remains a potential source of uncertainty.

Figure 12: Cloud coverage for observations grouped by slick detection status, showing the distribution of cloudy pixels in each class.

4.4.3 Angle of Incidence

The incidence azimuth angle governs the geometry of illumination and viewing in satellite imagery, influencing surface reflectance and apparent brightness. Analysing its distribution helps to assess potential directional biases in image acquisition. The histogram in Figure 13 shows the mean incidence azimuth angle for Band 1, illustrating the range of observation geometries present in the dataset.

The distribution reveals a predominance of extreme viewing geometries, with most observations acquired at high ($> 275^\circ$) or low ($\leq 125^\circ$) azimuth angles and relatively few near the nadir. This pattern suggests that the satellite predominantly captured scenes from oblique directions, likely reflecting orbital geometry, swath configuration, or targeted acquisitions over wreck sites. The under-representation of near-central angles has implications for both radiometric normalisation and model generalisation, as illumination geometry may introduce systematic variation in reflectance and classification performance.

Figure 13: Distribution of the mean incidence azimuth angle for Band 1 across all observations.

4.4.4 SAR Metadata Exploration and Label Refinement

Exploratory analysis of the wreck metadata was undertaken to derive additional features and assess label consistency. For the HMAS CANBERRA wreck, the number of masked pixels (*slick area*) was computed per image, and descriptive statistics (minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation) were calculated for three SAR bands within a cropped region covering all slicks and appended to the metadata.

Comparison of slick and non-slick subsets showed high variability in band statistics (B1_std ranging from 1.94–15.36 for non-slicks), indicating potential label inconsistencies or limited discriminatory power. A Gaussian-based label correction was then applied: pixel values from confirmed slicks were modelled per band, z -scores were computed for unlabelled images, and those with more than 1 000 low- z pixels were reclassified as slicks. The method identified candidate mislabels but produced inconsistent results, suggesting that band-level statistics alone were insufficient for reliable correction.

This procedure suggested inconsistencies within the original labels and suggested that a portion of the “non-slick” data likely contained unmarked slicks. However, the results were sensitive to threshold selection and did not yield a consistent

quantitative improvement, underscoring the need for more robust, model-based feature extraction in subsequent analyses.

5 Approach

To advance the automated detection of oil slicks from shipwrecks, this study addresses three interlinked challenges: preprocessing and harmonisation of multi-sensor imagery, integration of environmental and physical covariates, and the development of robust modelling frameworks for slick detection and prediction.

Research was structured around the following questions:

1. *How can datasets be effectively preprocessed and harmonised to preserve radiometric integrity while enabling analysis?*

Image data was high resolution and varied in spectral range and acquisition geometry. Preprocessing and exploration aimed to standardise inputs while preserving slick-related texture and radiometric detail and better understanding spectral correlations. Exploration included spatial resampling, incidence-angle and cloud correction, and use of foveated downsampling to retain central detail near wrecks while reducing data volume.

2. *How can contextual environmental and physical covariates be integrated to improve model realism and generalisation?*

Slick visibility was influenced by wind, wave height, temperature, and seismic activity. Meteorological and seismic data were aligned with satellite acquisitions to provide physical context, and derived variables such as wind extremes and quake recency were explored for potential influence on slick occurrence.

3. *What machine-learning architectures are most effective for detecting and predicting oil slicks across sensors and time?*

Exploration of deep-learning methods' performance in detecting slicks across spatial and temporal scales was conducted. Experiments compared pre-trained and newly trained models on harmonised datasets, assessed the benefit of combining SAR and MSI imagery, and evaluated the influence of

environmental covariates on classification and segmentation performance. Emphasis was placed on model generalisation across wreck sites and the integration of physically meaningful features.

Sections 6 through 9 of this report address each question in turn: data preprocessing and harmonisation, integration of environmental and physical covariates, and the evaluation of machine-learning architectures for detection and prediction across sensors and time.

6 Data Preprocessing

6.1 Image Downsampling

Raw images from the SAR and MSI datasets had a maximum spatial extent of approximately 2250×2250 pixels across 13 spectral bands, resulting in prohibitive memory requirements for direct model training. Conventional spatial reduction was first applied by cropping or resizing the imagery to standard input dimensions of 256×256 , 384×384 , and 512×512 pixels, ensuring manageable computational load while preserving key scene context.

6.2 Foveated Downsampling of SAR Data

The images comprising the dataset were highly spatially-imbalanced, with slick pixels occupying only a small fraction of each image relative to the background water class, leading to instability during model training. To address this, the majority (no-slick) class was downsampled to produce a more balanced training set. While this approach improved training stability, it also reduced information content by removing potentially useful samples and was therefore used cautiously given the limited dataset size. Nonetheless, downsampling yielded a measurable improvement in CNN classification performance.

Each image measured approximately [2 channels \times 250 pixels \times 2250 pixels] \approx 40.5 MB pixels, equivalent to about 40 MB at 32-bit depth. The data volume provided high spatial detail but required reduction to enable practical model training. As with sample downsampling, pixel downsampling removes potentially informative content. The process therefore represents a balance between computational efficiency and predictive fidelity.

In the slick detection task, pixel relevance is spatially uneven. Central regions

are more informative, as each image is centred on the known or inferred wreck site. A pixel downsampling method, termed *Foveated Downsampling* (FD), was developed and tested to preserve detail in these regions by retaining full spatial resolution near the image centre, while reducing resolution elsewhere to reduce overall input size and computational cost.

FD was initially proposed as an original approach. Subsequent review showed that foveation is a recognised principle in image and video processing, though no prior work was identified describing a pixel-based downsampling implementation equivalent to that used here.

The core principle of FD is to preserve central pixels and progressively reduce resolution toward the image edges, with information loss scaling by distance from the centre. The formal mathematical description of the method is provided below; the complete implementation is available in the project repository as the torch-compatible transform `FoveatedDownsampleBox`.

The foveated downsampling operator, denoted \mathbf{F}_B , defines a mapping from an input image $\mathbf{X}_{in} \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times H_{in} \times W_{in}}$ to an output image $\mathbf{X}_{out} \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times H_{out} \times W_{out}}$, where C is the number of channels and W and H are image widths and heights, respectively. This can be expressed as a functional mapping with zero-indexed pixel coordinates, consistent with the implementation:

$$\mathbf{X}_{in} : \{0, \dots, W_{in} - 1\} \times \{0, \dots, H_{in} - 1\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^C, \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{X}_{out} : \{0, \dots, W_{out} - 1\} \times \{0, \dots, H_{out} - 1\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^C. \quad (2)$$

The image centre c is defined for both the input and output images by their respective width and height midpoints:

$$c_x^{in} = \frac{W_{in} - 1}{2}, \quad c_y^{in} = \frac{H_{in} - 1}{2}, \quad c_x^{out} = \frac{W_{out} - 1}{2}, \quad c_y^{out} = \frac{H_{out} - 1}{2}. \quad (3)$$

The parameter $k = \frac{1}{2} \text{keep_px}$ is defined as half the side length of the central region where pixels remain unchanged. For each output pixel (x, y) , signed distances from the image centre are given by $d_x = x - c_x^{out}$ and $d_y = y - c_y^{out}$, with corresponding absolute distances $a_x = |d_x|$ and $a_y = |d_y|$. The half-extents from the output image centre to its horizontal and vertical borders were defined as $E_x = c_x^{out}$ and $E_y = c_y^{out}$.

The FD algorithm provided fine-grained control over the trade-off between data volume and information retention. It also enabled a controlled reduction in image dimensions to any desired output size, which was advantageous for models such as CNNs that require fixed input dimensions. All SAR deep learning models were trained using FD from $[2250 \times 2250] \rightarrow [250 \times 250]$ pixels. Figure 14 illustrates a slick mask before and after foveated downsampling, where image size was reduced by a factor of 81 while preserving most of the salient slick features.

(a) Original image mask $[2250 \times 2250]$ pixels (b) Image mask after Foveated Downsampling $[250 \times 250]$ pixels

Figure 14: Illustration of Foveated Downsampling on a SAR mask, with a) the original image and b) the image after downsampling

6.3 Weather Data Integration

To facilitate weather data fusion, integration was developed using three distinct datasets: i) Processed SAR images; ii) Corresponding mask labels; and iii) Meteorological data.

A Python-based data fusion pipeline was developed to consolidate these datasets into a unified .csv file for each identified wreck. The fusion process leveraged the timestamp as a common key across all datasets, enabling temporal alignment. Since both the SAR images and their associated mask labels contained extractable time metadata, this allowed for seamless synchronisation with the

weather data.

The resulting .csv files were structured chronologically, providing a time-series representation of environmental conditions leading up to and following the detection of oil slicks. This temporal organisation was critical for downstream analysis, particularly for training time-aware AI models.

Subsequently, a binary “slick” column was introduced to facilitate straightforward classification and feature extraction. This column was populated with binary values; “1” if a mask label was present, indicating the detection of an oil slick and “0” if the mask label was absent, signifying no slick detection. This method enabled efficient filtering and analysis of slick versus non-slick events on a per-record basis, streamlining both exploratory data analysis and model development.

6.4 Seismic Feature Integration

Seismic data were integrated with SAR imagery and weather observations to derive features suitable for modelling. Because seismic events were temporally sparse, each recorded earthquake was aligned with the nearest SAR acquisition, producing the derived variable `days_since_quake`. This variable was further transformed into `quake_recency` to quantify the temporal proximity of seismic activity to each observation. The transformation employed a logistic decay function, assigning greater weight to recent events while allowing the influence of older quakes to diminish smoothly over time. Unlike linear or exponential decay, the logistic formulation provides a flexible threshold effect in which events within a critical temporal window retain higher significance before the contribution declines sharply.

The transformation is defined as:

$$\text{quake_recency} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(k (\text{days_since_quake} - x_0))} \quad (4)$$

where k controls the steepness of the curve, and x_0 denotes the midpoint at which the influence of an event is reduced by half. In this study, $x_0 = 60$ days was assumed, corresponding to the characteristic timescale over which seismic effects on slick formation are expected to diminish.

Seismic magnitudes were reported using multiple related scales (mb, mww, mwc, mwb), all approximating moment magnitude through different data sources and

inversion methods. The m_b scale is based on P- and S-wave amplitudes, whereas the M_w variants employ seismic moment estimates derived from differing datasets and modelling approaches, reflecting trade-offs between accuracy and computational speed.

All m_b magnitudes were converted to moment magnitude using the empirical relationships proposed by [7]:

$$M_w = 0.85 m_b + 1.03 \quad \text{for } m_b \geq 3.5 \quad (5)$$

The distance between each seismic event and the corresponding wreck site was calculated using the haversine formula, yielding great-circle distances in kilometres. The hypocentral distance, representing the combined effect of epicentral distance and earthquake depth, was then derived as a single scalar quantity using the Pythagorean relationship.

7 Binary Classification of MSI Data

Initial experiments focused on binary classification of MSI data, treating slick detection as an image-level prediction problem. A temporal sequence modelling framework was developed using MSI data to perform binary classification of oil slick presence around shipwrecks. Rather than relying on pixel-level segmentation masks, the approach utilised metadata-derived annotations indicating slick occurrence at each acquisition. Sentinel-2 metadata, including ship identifiers, acquisition timestamps, and detection flags, was used to construct temporally ordered input sequences for model training and evaluation.

Two complementary data loaders were implemented to exploit the spatial and temporal structure of the dataset. The window-based loader grouped fixed-length contiguous frames to capture local spatio-temporal patterns, supporting models such as a 3D CNN, Random Forest, and PINN. The sequence-based loader arranged temporally ordered frames to enable architectures like Convolutional Neural Network - Long Short-Term Memory (CNN-LSTM) models to capture longer-range temporal dependencies across acquisitions.

Using the two data representations, windows and sequences, models were trained on a subset of shipwrecks to learn temporal patterns in slick formation and evolution. Evaluation was performed on entirely unseen sites to assess model

generalisation to new wrecks under varying environmental and observational conditions.

Owing to limited GPU resources, the analysis focused on lightweight architectures for temporal slick classification. Alongside the 3D CNN, Random Forest, and PINN trained with the window-based loader, a SAR–optical fusion model was developed, incorporating a gating mechanism to regulate modality expressiveness, followed by a Kronecker product to capture pairwise cross-modal feature interactions. The training dataset comprised only two shipwrecks (MV BRITISH LOYALTY and USS ATLANTA), while all remaining sites were reserved as an independent test set.

7.1 Window-Based Data Loader Models

To facilitate temporal modelling, slick annotations were converted into binary labels (1 for slick present, 0 for no slick). Image filenames were parsed to extract acquisition timestamps, and metadata records were used to generate a lookup table linking each timestamp to its corresponding class label.

For each ship, images were chronologically ordered, and a fixed-length sliding window of three consecutive acquisitions was applied. Each window constituted a single training sample, labelled according to the final timestamp to provide supervision on slick presence while incorporating preceding temporal context. Each sample was stored as a tuple containing the ship identifier, the ordered sequence of file paths, and the associated label.

During data loading, images were read band by band from the GeoTIFF files, resized to a uniform spatial resolution of 64×64 pixels, and normalised to the $[0, 1]$ range. Each temporal sequence was stacked into a tensor of shape (T, C, H, W) , where T denotes the temporal window length, C the number of MSI spectral channels, and (H, W) the spatial dimensions. In this configuration, the sequence length L was set to three. The algorithm summary is presented in Appendix A.

7.1.1 3D CNN

A lightweight 3D convolutional neural network (3D CNN) was implemented to model the spatio-temporal dynamics of slick formation. Unlike conventional CNNs that capture only spatial features, 3D convolutions extend across both spatial

and temporal dimensions, enabling the network to learn spectral-spatial patterns as they evolve through consecutive observations. This temporal representation is critical for detecting slicks, whose formation and dissipation are inherently time-dependent. The architecture was aligned with the window-based data loader, which produces fixed-length, time-ordered Sentinel-2 MSI sequences represented as tensors of shape (T, C, H, W) , where T denotes the temporal axis.

Figure 15: Architecture of the lightweight 3D CNN used for temporal MSI sequence classification.

The 3D CNN was trained for binary slick classification by minimising the cross-entropy loss between predicted probabilities and ground-truth labels:

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log \frac{\exp(z_{i,y_i})}{\sum_{c=0}^1 \exp(z_{i,c})}, \quad (6)$$

where N is the number of samples in a batch and z_{i,y_i} denotes the logit corresponding to the true class.

Discussion

The dataset was highly imbalanced between slick-present and slick-absent samples. To address this, a `WeightedRandomSampler` was applied during training, assigning sample weights inversely proportional to class frequency. Slick-present instances therefore appeared more frequently in mini-batches, ensuring that both classes contributed comparably to the optimisation process and reducing bias toward the majority class.

An initial 80/20 train-validation split using MV BRITISH LOYALTY and USS ATLANTA yielded an accuracy of 0.81. To prevent data leakage, the trained model was subsequently evaluated on each remaining wreck independently (MV BRITISH LOYALTY, USS ATLANTA, IJN HIEI, ORP KUJAWIAK, IJN KIRISHIMA, SS COIMBRA, HMS PoW), achieving an average accuracy of 0.63.

The model was trained for five epochs. Training loss exhibited a consistent downward trend, whereas validation loss fluctuated, suggesting that additional epochs and a larger dataset would likely improve training stability and generalisation.

Figure 16: Training and validation loss curves for 3D CNN.

Despite balanced resampling, the model continued to produce a high rate of false positives, achieving an average precision of 0.128 for slick detection. Expanding the training dataset is expected to improve precision and reduce misclassification of non-slick observations.

Figure 17: Comparison of 3D CNN confusion matrices for (a) independent wreck sites and (b) ORP KUJAWIAK.

7.1.2 Random Forest

Feature extraction converted each sequence into a five-dimensional tensor (batch, time, channel, height, width). For every frame and spectral channel, summary statistics including mean, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, and temporal change in mean were computed and concatenated into flattened feature vectors for input to the Random Forest classifier.

Training on the two selected wrecks with an 80/20 split yielded an accuracy of 0.87. When evaluated on independent wrecks to prevent temporal leakage, accuracy decreased to 0.76. Precision for slick detection remained low 0.12, despite a recall of 0.448, indicating frequent false positives. These limitations were primarily attributed to the restricted train–test split (0.13 / 0.87) and the persistent effects of class imbalance.

The Random Forest classifier was observed to be computationally lightweight in practice, enabling validation across multiple wrecks; no formal inference time benchmarking was performed. In contrast, deep learning models were limited to one or two sites due to computational and memory constraints, restricting their generalisability assessment.

Figure 18: Random Forest confusion matrix on independent test wrecks.

The model performed best on wrecks included in training and showed limited generalisation to unseen sites such as HMAS CASSANDRA and ORP KUJAWIAK. For the latter, precision and recall were both 0.22, under conditions of extreme class imbalance and limited annotated data.

The ORP KUJAWIAK site is of particular interest, being located near a fish farm and exhibiting more frequent slick events than other wrecks. Model performance at this site was higher than at other unseen locations; however, given the small size of the training set and extreme class imbalance, this difference cannot be reliably attributed to site-specific characteristics.

7.1.3 MSI-SAR Fusion

A bilinear fusion module was developed to integrate MSI and SAR features within a unified representation. Unlike feature concatenation, bilinear fusion models pairwise interactions between modalities, enabling the network to learn richer cross-modal dependencies. A gating-based attention mechanism was incorporated to regulate the relative contribution of each modality and suppress less informative signals, thereby enhancing expressiveness and regularisation. The fusion process can be expressed mathematically as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{h}_{m, \text{gated}} &= \mathbf{z}_m * \mathbf{h}_m, \quad m \in \{i, g\} \\
\mathbf{h}_m &= \text{ReLU}(W_m \cdot \mathbf{h}_m) \\
\mathbf{z}_m &= \sigma(W_{ig \rightarrow m} \cdot [\mathbf{h}_i, \mathbf{h}_g]).
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where \mathbf{h}_i and \mathbf{h}_g denote the modality-specific feature embeddings, $m \in \{i, g\}$ indexes modality, W_m and $W_{ig \rightarrow m}$ are learned projection matrices and \mathbf{z}_m are modality-specific gating vectors. To preserve unimodal information, a constant term was appended to each modality before computing bilinear interactions through a Kronecker product-like operation. This produced a high-dimensional fused representation capturing both unimodal and cross-modal features. The fused outputs were projected through fully connected encoders with optional skip connections to obtain a compact joint embedding. This design enabled efficient integration of complementary SAR and MSI signals while maintaining computational tractability, making it suitable for multimodal learning tasks requiring explicit feature interaction modelling.

Bilinear fusion was applied to combine the embeddings generated by the 3D CNNs for the SAR and MSI modalities. On the limited validation set comprising MV BRITISH LOYALTY and USS ATLANTA, validation accuracy increased from 0.81 to 0.938. However, this result is based on a very small experimental set and a single training epoch, and occasional NaN losses were observed, indicating numerical instability and limiting the strength of any conclusions.

7.1.4 PINNs

PINNs were considered for implementation by augmenting the learning objective with a physics-based loss term. The evolution of the scalar concentration field $C(x, y, t)$ would be modelled using the two-dimensional advection–diffusion equation:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} = D \nabla^2 C, \quad \nabla^2 C = \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} \tag{8}$$

where u, v are velocity components and D is the diffusion coefficient, x and y denote continuous physical spatial coordinates corresponding to the image plane previously indexed by pixel height H and width W . t denotes time. In this formulation, $\frac{\partial C}{\partial t}$ represents the rate of change of surface oil concentration, $u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x}$

and $v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y}$ advection by currents or wind, and $D \nabla^2 C$ denotes diffusion arising from mixing and turbulence. The advection–diffusion equation therefore characterises slick transport and spreading as a balance between temporal variation, advective drift, and diffusive dispersion, forming a standard physical basis for fluid-dynamic and environmental modelling.

The PINN framework was not possible to implement due to the absence of direct concentration measurements. Two potential strategies were identified to address this limitation: (i) estimating concentration from slick masks by relating areal extent and pixel distribution to image resolution, and (ii) approximating concentration from model confidence scores, under the assumption that higher predictive confidence correlates with increased slick intensity, potentially calibrated through a post-hoc adjustment procedure.

7.2 Sequence-Based Data Loader Models

In addition to the window-based approach, a sequence-based data loader was implemented to support models capable of capturing longer temporal dependencies, such as CNN–LSTM architectures. The labelling scheme remained consistent, assigning binary labels (1 for slick present, 0 for no slick) derived from the metadata to the final timestamp of each sequence.

Unlike the window-based loader, which retained all MSI channels, the sequence-based loader applied preprocessing steps to reduce spectral redundancy and emphasise the most informative bands. Channels were condensed into compact representations, including RGB composites (bands 4, 3, and 2), alternative RGB variants, the Ocean Slick Index (OSI), and the Normalised Difference Ocean Slick Index (NDOSI). These transformations reduced computational cost while preserving the spectral features most relevant to slick detection.

Because Sentinel-2 acquisitions cover extensive spatial areas, images were cropped to regions surrounding known wreck coordinates. The original 2250×2250 -pixel patches were reduced to 224×224 crops centred on each wreck, improving computational efficiency and constraining the analysis to areas where slick formation is most probable.

As in the window-based approach, the resulting sequences were stored as tensors, with dimensions adjusted to reflect the reduced channel count and cropped spatial resolution. This configuration ensured that models were trained on temporally

ordered, spatially localised inputs preserving both the temporal evolution of slicks and the most relevant spectral characteristics.

7.2.1 CNN-LSTM Model and Method

To capture spatial structure within individual MSI frames and temporal dependencies across observations, a CNN–LSTM architecture was implemented. A pretrained ResNet-18 backbone initialised on ImageNet was used to extract high-level spatial representations from each frame. The final fully connected layer was replaced with an identity mapping, producing a 512-dimensional feature vector per frame. Backbone parameters were frozen during training to reduce computational cost and mitigate overfitting, given the limited dataset size.

The sequence of frame-level embeddings was passed to a long short-term memory (LSTM) module to model the temporal evolution of slick patterns. The LSTM comprised a single recurrent layer with a hidden size of 256. For classification, the hidden state corresponding to the central frame in each temporal window was selected, allowing predictions to be informed by both preceding and subsequent context. This state was passed through a fully connected layer to produce binary predictions of slick presence or absence.

To address the pronounced class imbalance between slick and non-slick samples, a focal loss function was adopted to stabilise training and emphasise hard-to-classify examples. Focal loss extends standard cross-entropy by introducing a modulating factor $(1 - p_t)^\gamma$, where p_t denotes the predicted probability of the true class. This formulation down-weights well-classified instances while concentrating optimisation on misclassified and minority-class samples. Formally, the focal loss is expressed as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{focal}} = -\alpha_t(1 - p_t)^\gamma \log(p_t), \quad (9)$$

where $\alpha_t \in [0, 1]$ is a weighting factor that balances the importance of positive and negative samples, and $\gamma \geq 0$ is the focusing parameter controlling how strongly the loss down-weights easy examples.

For the binary classification setting in this work, the loss can be written as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{focal}} = -\alpha y (1 - p)^\gamma \log(p) - (1 - \alpha)(1 - y) p^\gamma \log(1 - p), \quad (10)$$

where $y \in \{0, 1\}$ is the ground-truth label and p is the predicted probability of the positive class.

In all experiments, the focusing parameter was set to $\gamma = 2.0$ and the weighting factor $\alpha = 0.75$ to balance the contribution of positive (slick present) and negative (no slick) samples.

To assess the generalisation capability of the CNN–LSTM model, a leave-one-wreck-out cross-validation strategy was employed. The dataset comprised four wrecks, with one held out for testing in each fold. The remaining three were divided into two for training and one for validation. This protocol ensured that evaluation was always performed on an unseen wreck, providing a rigorous measure of model transferability across varying environmental conditions and sites.

In each fold, data were prepared using the sequence-based loader with a temporal window of five frames. Samples were normalised using the standard ImageNet mean and standard deviation before model input. Training was conducted for up to 20 epochs using the Adam optimiser with a learning rate 1×10^{-3} , and early stopping with a patience of three epochs was applied to mitigate overfitting.

Model performance was evaluated using accuracy, F1-score, and confusion matrices. After completion of all folds, test results were aggregated across wrecks to yield an overall assessment of the CNN–LSTM model’s generalisation performance. The results in Table 2 indicate that the model exhibited limited effectiveness in handling the severe class imbalance present in the dataset.

Although accuracy remained high across training, validation, and test splits, this reflected the predominance of negative samples rather than genuine predictive capability. More informative metrics, precision and F1-score, remained low, with average values of *Test Precision* = 0.279 and *Test F1* = 0.179 across folds. The best-performing fold (Fold 3, MV MY BRITISH LOYALTY) achieved *Test Precision* = 0.337 and *Test F1* = 0.306, representing a modest improvement yet underscoring the difficulty of detecting rare positive cases. These results demonstrate that, under severe class imbalance, overall accuracy is a misleading indicator of model performance.

7.3 Data Augmentation

To mitigate overfitting, additional data augmentation methods were explored. Conventional approaches such as additive noise or geometric distortion were

Table 2: Values of the average, and best performing Fold (Fold 3) Cross-validation results for CNN-LSTM model.

Metric	Accuracy	Precision	F1
Avg. Across all Folds			
Train	0.909	0.795	0.483
Val	0.812	0.065	0.092
Test	0.824	0.279	0.179
Fold 3			
Train	0.910	0.709	0.735
Val	0.763	0.195	0.277
Test	0.795	0.337	0.306

unsuitable, as they degrade SAR backscatter integrity. A speckle filter applied during preprocessing reduced stochastic variance without compromising key spatial features. Augmentation therefore focused on generating physically consistent variability within slick and non-slick classes. Sequence reversal simulated dissipative slick evolution, while controlled surface perturbations increased intra-class diversity. Representative confounders, including algal blooms and biogenic films, were incorporated to improve discrimination. Weighted sampling further addressed class imbalance, increasing model exposure to minority positive instances.

The following data augmentation methods were implemented: i) Temporal reversal, simulating the reverse progression of slick dynamics; ii) Spatial flips, accounting for orientation invariance; iii) Morphological operations (dilation and erosion), replicating the natural expansion or contraction of slick boundaries; iv) Elastic warping, reproducing deformations caused by ocean currents or turbulence; and v) Temporal dropout, removing entire frames to emulate missing satellite observations.

A *difficulty-based augmentation strategy* was also tested, in which augmentation strength was adapted to model confidence. High-confidence (easy) samples received stronger perturbations, while low-confidence (hard) samples were modified conservatively. This approach improved model robustness while maintaining sensitivity to minority cases.

8 Binary Classification of SAR Data

Binary classification was subsequently applied to SAR data, where backscatter characteristics present distinct challenges relative to optical imagery. Exploratory baseline models and full image-based methods were employed for the binary classification of oil slick presence in SAR data. Approaches included logistic regression and random forest, as well as higher-capacity architectures such as CNNs and ViTs. These models were evaluated to examine detection behaviour using multiple levels of model complexity under significant class imbalance, to establish insight into multiple modelling frameworks.

8.1 Exploratory Modelling of SAR Data

Exploratory modelling was undertaken on the SAR dataset using three baseline classifiers: logistic regression (with imbalanced data), random forest (imbalanced), and random forest (class-balanced 50:50). These models were trained and evaluated on the same dataset and were employed solely for exploratory assessment of variable associations rather than predictive validation.

Each model examined the relationship between oil slick occurrence and four environmental covariates: i) surface wave height (*sw_h*), ii) wind velocity (*wind_v*), iii) sea surface temperature (*sst*), and iv) air temperature at 2 m (*t2m*). The dependent variable was binary (0 = no slick, 1 = slick). Each SAR acquisition was linked to its corresponding binary mask and synchronised with the nearest three-hourly observation from the integrated weather dataset. This enabled evaluation of short-term environmental influences on slick presence at wreck sites.

The analysis aimed to determine whether localised meteorological variability could explain slick occurrence. Strong class imbalance constrained sensitivity, as slick events were infrequent relative to non-slick observations. Temporal alignment between SAR captures and weather records allowed direct comparison of environmental parameters with observed slick events. Model performance was assessed using standard classification metrics (AUROC, accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score), and variable coefficients and feature importances were examined to interpret the relative influence of each environmental factor.

Logistic regression was employed as an initial baseline owing to its interpretability,

computational efficiency, and capacity to quantify the relative contribution of each predictor variable through its model coefficients.

A Random Forest classifier was implemented on balanced and imbalanced data to assess whether non-linear relationships or variable interactions could improve discrimination performance. Random Forests, as ensemble methods based on aggregated decision trees, are inherently more robust to noise and outliers and can model complex dependencies between predictors. They also provide feature importance metrics, enabling evaluation of the relative contribution of environmental variables to slick occurrence. To address the persistent class imbalance, the dataset was resampled using random undersampling of the majority class. Each positive (“mask”) instance was paired with a randomly selected negative (“no-mask”) observation to achieve a balanced 1:1 ratio. This ensured equal weighting of both classes during training, an essential condition for evaluating model behaviour on the minority slick class.

Performance metrics for logistic regression are summarised in Table 3. Results indicated limited predictive discrimination, consistent with the small number of slick observations. Coefficient magnitudes suggested that higher sea surface temperature (-0.98) and greater wave height (-0.74) were negatively associated with slick occurrence, whereas air temperature (+0.84) showed a positive relationship. Wind velocity (-0.54) exhibited a weak negative influence. These relationships align with expectations that calmer and cooler conditions are more conducive to visible slick persistence.

Table 3: Performance metrics of exploratory modelling by logistic regression

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
Class 0 (No Slick)	0.97	0.55	0.70	2297
Class 1 (Slick)	0.10	0.76	0.17	147

Model evaluation yielded an AUROC of 0.70, indicating discriminative capacity above random but insufficient for reliable classification. Owing to the pronounced class imbalance, the model exhibited bias toward the majority “no slick” class, producing an inflated overall accuracy but limited utility for rare-event detection. Precision for the slick class was low (0.10), reflecting a high rate of false positives, while recall remained comparatively high (0.76), indicating that most slick events were detected but at the expense of substantial misclassification of non-slick observations.

Logistic Regression provided interpretable coefficients consistent with physical expectations but showed limited discriminative power under severe class imbalance. While recall for slicks was relatively high, the abundance of false positives resulted in a weak F1-score, confirming that more flexible, non-linear models were required to capture the environmental dependencies underlying slick formation.

Performance metrics for Random Forest on imbalanced data are summarised in Table 4. The model achieved modest improvement in both AUROC and overall accuracy relative to logistic regression but remained strongly biased toward the majority (no-slick) class.

Table 4: Classification Report: Random Forest (Imbalanced Data)

Metric	Class 0 (No Slick)	Class 1 (Slick)
Precision	0.94	0.42
Recall	0.99	0.07
F1-score	0.97	0.13
Support	2297	147

Recall for slicks was extremely low, indicating poor sensitivity and limited operational suitability where missed detections are critical. Feature importance analysis suggested that significant wave height (0.29) and wind velocity (0.26) were the dominant predictors, followed by sea surface temperature (0.23) and air temperature (0.22). These results imply that surface dynamics exerted greater influence on model output than thermal variables, yet the imbalance problem continued to limit discriminative performance.

Performance metrics for a Random Forest on balanced data are summarised in Table 5. Balancing the dataset substantially improved model discrimination and stability. Training on the 1:1 class-balanced data achieved an AUROC of 0.77 and an overall accuracy of 0.71, representing the strongest performance among the tested models. For the slick class, precision (0.71), recall (0.75), and F1-score (0.73) indicated consistent sensitivity and specificity, while performance for the non-slick class remained comparably strong. The balanced sampling strategy effectively mitigated the prior bias toward the majority class, enabling more equitable classification across both categories and demonstrating the potential of resampling to improve rare-event detection in limited datasets.

The progression from logistic regression to the balanced random forest underscores

Table 5: Classification Report: Random Forest (Balanced Data)

Metric	Class 0 (No Slick)	Class 1 (Slick)
Precision	0.70	0.71
Recall	0.66	0.75
F1-score	0.68	0.73
Support	122	136

the influence of class imbalance on environmental classification performance. Logistic regression offered interpretability but limited robustness, whereas the Random Forest models captured non-linear relationships and variable interactions more effectively.

Balancing the training data was essential to achieving unbiased and reliable classification. The non-linear Random Forest model demonstrated the strongest and most consistent performance across metrics, capturing key environmental interactions while maintaining interpretability through feature importance analysis. Significant wave height and wind velocity emerged as the dominant predictors of slick occurrence, consistent with physical expectations of surface dynamics influencing oil dispersion and persistence.

8.2 Full-Scale Binary Classification of SAR Data

A unified probabilistic framework for joint occurrence and recurrence assessment was not pursued due to limited positive samples, sparse annotations, and computational constraints. The problem was therefore addressed using a set of complementary models to estimate slick occurrence at shipwreck sites: (i) a Vision Transformer (ViT) for single- and multi-image SAR classification; (ii) a Transformer trained on environmental (ERA5 wind, sea-surface temperature, air temperature, and wave) and seismic time series; and (iii) baseline convolutional neural networks (CNNs) of differing depth with class weightings of 1.0 for negatives and 3.0 for positives. Each model was trained and evaluated independently under consistent data partitions, providing a basis for subsequent integration toward persistence and recurrence modelling.

8.2.1 ViTs

Slick detection from SAR imagery was formulated as supervised binary classification, assigning $y = 1$ when a slick mask was present and $y = 0$ otherwise. Two configurations were used:

- single-image input $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times H \times W}$ (VV, VH polarisations),
- and short-sequence input $\mathbf{X}_{t-N:t} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times C \times H \times W}$ formed by channel-wise concatenation of consecutive images.

A lightweight ViT was applied in both cases, dividing each image into fixed-size patches treated as sequence tokens to capture spatial dependencies through self-attention.

8.2.2 Time Series Transformer

Time-series modelling of weather and seismic data used input sequences $\mathbf{x}_{t-N:t} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$, where each $\mathbf{x}_t \in \mathbb{R}^D$ represents D environmental features at time t . The corresponding timestamps $t_{t-N:t} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ were provided as an additional input. Given a query time t_q , the model estimates the probability of slick occurrence as

$$P(\text{slick at } t_q \mid \mathbf{x}_{t-N:t}, t_{t-N:t}) = f(t_q, \mathbf{x}_{t-N:t}, t_{t-N:t}),$$

where $f(\cdot)$ denotes the Transformer-based predictor. Each timestamp t was decomposed into *time of day*, *day of year*, and *year*, then mapped through sinusoidal time embeddings to provide a periodic representation of temporal structure.

Sinusoidal time embeddings (STE) employ a fixed, non-trainable function that encodes each timestamp t as a vector $\mathbf{t} \in \mathbb{R}^P$, where the p^{th} element is given by $\text{STE}_p(t)$. This representation provides a continuous, periodic encoding of time suitable for Transformer-based sequence models.

$$\text{STE}_p(t) = \begin{cases} \sin\left(\frac{s t}{B^{2i/P}}\right), & \text{if } p \text{ odd,} \\ \cos\left(\frac{s t}{B^{2i/P}}\right), & \text{if } p \text{ even,} \end{cases} \quad i = \lfloor p/2 \rfloor, \quad p \in \{1, \dots, P\}, \quad (11)$$

where B is the base frequency (set to 10,000) and $s = \frac{2\pi}{T}$, with T denoting the characteristic period of t (24 h for time of day, 365.25 days for day of year). The

embedding $\text{STE}(t)$ was added to each input vector as $\mathbf{x}_t + \text{STE}(t)$, enabling the model to represent periodic temporal dependencies.

After time embedding, all time-series elements and the query time were projected into a shared vector space. A multi-head self-attention mechanism computed the relevance of each element with respect to the query time, and the resulting attention weights were used to form a query-specific weighted representation from which the final prediction was derived.

8.2.3 Transformer Model Training

The ViT and temporal Transformer were trained with identical hyperparameters to ensure comparability. Each model was trained for 100 epochs using the Adam optimiser (learning rate 1×10^{-3} , weight decay 1×10^{-2}) and a batch size of 32. Binary cross-entropy loss with a positive-class weighting of 10 addressed the strong slick/non-slick imbalance. Inputs were downsampled to 250×250 pixels using foveated sampling ($\text{KEEP_PX}=128$, $\gamma = 2.0$) to retain high-information regions near wreck centres. Transformer encoders employed a hidden dimension of 64, eight attention heads, and positional embeddings over ten spatial patches. Temporal sequence length was $T_{\text{len}} = 1$ for the ViT and 12 for the time-series model. Training, validation, and testing used fixed directory splits for reproducibility on CUDA-enabled hardware.

8.2.4 CNNs

Two convolutional architectures were implemented as baselines for SAR image classification. Both were trained under a consistent pipeline for comparability. Input images were downsampled to 256×256 pixels using foveated sampling ($\text{keep_px}=128$, $\gamma = 2.0$) and loaded in mini-batches of 8 with balanced positive and negative samples. Training employed the Adam optimiser (1×10^{-4} learning rate) with gradient clipping ($\|\nabla\|_{\text{max}} = 5.0$) and weighted cross-entropy loss to address class imbalance. The *Baseline CNN* (three convolutional blocks) was trained for 10 epochs with a fixed class weight ratio of 1:3 (no-slick:slick) to penalise false negatives, while maintaining approximately balanced sampling across batches. The Deep CNN (six convolutional layers with dropout) was trained for twenty epochs using dynamic class weights derived from observed class frequencies. Both used identical validation protocols and post-training evaluation through accuracy, classification reports, and confusion matrices.

8.2.5 Transformer and CNN Implementation

A fully fused model combining metadata time series and image inputs was not implemented; instead, two separate models were developed. The first was a Vision Transformer (ViT) for single- and multi-image classification, and the second a time-conditioned Transformer for time-series classification. Both models incorporated a `model.get_reps(input)` method that returned vector representations of their respective inputs, which could be concatenated and passed to a lightweight classifier head to enable future model fusion.

Because the slick versus non-slick dataset was highly imbalanced, classification accuracy was not a reliable indicator, as a trivial model predicting only the majority class could reach about 95% accuracy. Evaluation therefore used *Average Precision* (AP) and *Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve* (AUROC), both suitable for imbalanced data. AUROC is particularly informative, as a random classifier yields 0.5, and higher values indicate genuine predictive skill.

Two additional metrics were used: *average true negative probability mass* (ATNPM) and *average true positive probability mass* (ATPPM), defined as the mean predicted probabilities for true negative and true positive samples, respectively. While the ideal ATNPM and ATPPM are 0.0 and 1.0, their difference more directly reflects the model’s ability to assign higher probabilities to positive samples than to negative ones.

The ViT models were evaluated in two configurations: the first using individual SAR images and the second using short sequences of consecutive images.

Model	AUROC (↑)	AP (↑)	ATNPM (↓)	ATPPM (↑)
ViT (single image)	0.649	0.115	0.085	0.221
ViT (multi-image)	0.681	0.243	0.654	0.664

Table 6: Performance of ViT models for the binary classification task. Models were trained on data from one group of wrecks and evaluated on another, with no data overlap. Up and down arrows indicate whether higher or lower metric values denote better performance.

The single-image ViT achieved an AUROC of 0.6485 and an average precision of 0.1153, with mean predicted probabilities of 0.221 and 0.085 for true positives and true negatives, respectively.

When evaluated on sequences of three consecutive images, performance improved across all metrics: AUROC increased to 0.6808, average precision more than doubled to 0.2426, and mean predicted probabilities rose to 0.664 for true positives and 0.654 for true negatives.

Building on these image-based results, the time-series models were trained on metadata features, which were incorporated by their concatenation into the input feature vector for each time step. The first used only SAR metadata and weather variables, while the second incorporated seismic data to assess whether earthquake activity contributed additional predictive value.

Model	AUROC (\uparrow)	AP (\uparrow)	ATNPM (\downarrow)	ATPPM (\uparrow)
TC Transformer (w/o earthquake data)	0.487	0.0418	0.347	0.339
TC Transformer (w/o earthquake data)	0.4473	0.0382	0.381	0.343

Table 7: Performance of Time-Conditioned Transformer models for the binary classification task on time-series data. All models were trained on data from one set of wrecks and evaluated on data from a different set of wrecks, with no data overlap. Up arrows indicate higher metric value is better and vice versa.

The first model, trained on SAR and weather metadata, achieved an AUROC of 0.4869, an average precision of 0.0418, and mean predicted probabilities of 0.339 and 0.347 for true positives and true negatives, respectively, with a final loss of 0.9851.

The second model, which also incorporated seismic data, yielded an AUROC of 0.4473, an average precision of 0.0382, and mean predicted probabilities of 0.343 and 0.381 for true positives and true negatives, respectively. These results indicate slightly higher class-separation scores when earthquake data were included but lower overall discriminative performance. Any AUROC value below 0.5 implies performance no better than random, suggesting limited predictive power on unseen data.

In parallel with the ViT experiments, four convolutional baselines (M1–M4) were evaluated to examine how architectural depth and class-weighting strategies affected SAR slick detection performance.

Results for CNN model performance are summarised in Table 8. The small CNN baseline (M1) performed poorly, with an AUROC near 0.5, equivalent to random guessing. Introducing class weights (M2) marginally improved calibration but not overall accuracy. In contrast, the deeper CNN (M3) achieved a substantially higher AUROC of 0.79 and improved precision, demonstrating that increased depth enables richer SAR feature extraction. Applying class weighting to the deeper CNN (M4) produced further gains, particularly in recall for minority cases.

Model	AUROC (\uparrow)	AP (\uparrow)	ATNPM (\downarrow)	ATPPM (\uparrow)
M1 – Baseline CNN	0.50	0.33	0.50	0.00
M2 – Baseline CNN + weights	0.54	0.36	0.47	0.21
M3 – Deep CNN	0.79	0.44	0.66	0.81
M4 – Deep CNN + weights	0.81	0.46	0.64	0.83

Table 8: Performance of CNN models for the binary classification task. Up arrows indicate higher metric value is better and vice versa. Values approximate from validation results.

Overall, the deeper CNN configurations demonstrated competitive performance, with M4 outperforming both ViT configurations across most metrics.

9 Semantic Slick Detection of MSI Data

Semantic segmentation was investigated as a means of extending detection to pixel-level spatial delineation of slick extent. Three established semantic segmentation architectures were selected for evaluation, drawing on demonstrated performance in other domains. UNet was chosen for its encoder–decoder design with skip connections, enabling precise boundary recovery. DeepLabV3+ employs atrous spatial pyramid pooling for multi-scale feature extraction, and PSPNet incorporates pyramid scene parsing to capture global context. Two backbone networks were examined: ResNet50 for strong residual feature learning, and EfficientNet-b4 for improved efficiency–performance balance under computational constraints [2].

9.1 Implementation

The Sentinel-2 MSI segmentation pipeline uses multispectral optical imagery for oil spill detection and environmental monitoring. Figure 19 shows the four-stage process that converts MSI data into a raster mask that indicates the segmentation of slicks and water.

Figure 19: Overview of the Sentinel Optical Data Processing: Preprocessing (Spatial Dimension Selection and Dimensionality Reduction) and Model Training (Architectures and backbones).

To reduce the computational cost of processing 13-band images at full 2250² resolution, two spatial strategies were evaluated: resizing inputs to standard dimensions (256 × 256, 384 × 384, 512 × 512 pixels) to retain scene context efficiently, and patching full-resolution imagery into non-overlapping tiles to preserve fine spatial detail. This comparison balances spatial fidelity against computational efficiency and informs the selection of optimal processing configurations for model development.

The experiments covered 36 model configurations (3 architectures × 2 backbones × 2 spatial methods × 3 input sizes), allowing systematic evaluation of each component’s effect on performance.

All configurations used identical hyperparameters: batch size 8, an 8:2 train–validation split (image-level to prevent leakage), learning rate 1×10^{-4} with weight decay, AdamW optimiser, and up to 300 epochs with early stopping after 20 epochs without Slick IoU improvement. Mixed-precision training was applied to reduce memory use, and spectral integrity was maintained by omitting augmentations that could distort band characteristics.

To mitigate severe class imbalance, a composite loss combining focal loss [4] and Dice loss [8] was used to improve minority-class sensitivity while preserving overall segmentation accuracy.

Comprehensive quantitative results comparing semantic segmentation model performance across all configurations are presented in Appendix B. Model

Figure 20: Examples of 384×384 patch-based segmentation outputs from the PSPNet-ResNet50 model. The top row shows the ground truth masks, and the bottom row shows the corresponding model predictions. In both ground truth and predictions, blue represents the water body/background, orange represents oil slick, and brown represents land mass.

performance was evaluated using segmentation-specific metrics appropriate to the spatial nature of the task. Mean Intersection over Union (mIoU) and mean F1-score (mF1) were adopted as aggregate indicators of segmentation quality, reflecting the degree of overlap between predicted and ground-truth segments across all classes. Per-class IoU and F1-score were also reported, as aggregate measures can obscure performance disparities arising from class imbalance.

The patch-based approach performed best for oil slick detection, achieving a mean IoU of 0.67 versus 0.66 for resizing. Although the 0.011 IoU gain appears small, it corresponds to a 0.03 increase in mean F1 0.71 vs. 0.68, indicating materially

improved segmentation accuracy.

Most significantly, the patch-based method achieved an average IoU of 0.13, compared with 0.05 for resizing, representing a 2.7-fold improvement. The best configuration, PSPNet–ResNet50 with 256×256 patches, achieved 0.18 IoU and 0.28 F1, the highest minority-class performance across all tested configurations. Nevertheless, absolute minority-class performance remains poor, falling well short of operational utility, a limitation attributable to severe class imbalance and the spectral similarity between oil slicks and natural look-alikes.

Other Class-Specific Performance:

- **Background Class:** Both approaches achieved comparable performance (> 0.97 IoU, > 0.98 F1). However, given the severe class imbalance, this is an expected outcome and offers limited diagnostic value.
- **Land Class:** Interestingly, the resizing approach achieved better land detection (0.95 vs. 0.90 average IoU), likely due to preserved global context that aids in distinguishing large land masses from water bodies.

PSPNet demonstrated the most consistent performance across configurations and achieved peak performance for both processing approaches. The pyramid scene parsing module's ability to capture multi-scale contextual information appears particularly beneficial for the complex spatial patterns in oil spill scenarios.

For operational oil spill monitoring systems prioritising detection accuracy, the patch-based approach with 256×256 pixel patches using PSPNet architectures with ResNet50 backbone represents the most promising configuration tested. This configuration provides optimal balance between oil slick detection sensitivity and overall segmentation performance.

The challenging nature of oil slick detection (best performance: 0.18 IoU) indicates substantial room for improvement. Future work should investigate: (1) specialised architectures targeting under-represented class performance, (2) multi-scale fusion techniques combining patch and global context, (3) attention mechanisms designed for oil slick spectral signatures, and (4) advanced sampling and augmentation strategies that preserve spectral characteristics while improving minority class representation.

9.2 Grouped K-Fold Cross Validation

Oil-slick delineation from satellite imagery is affected by physical factors (e.g. coastline morphology, water optics, acquisition geometry). Randomly splitting image tiles into train/validation can therefore leak near-duplicate content across splits (adjacent patches, same overpass), inflating validation accuracy. To estimate performance on *unseen locations*, we use *grouped K-fold cross-validation* in which all samples from the same site are assigned to the same fold.

Let $\mathcal{D} = \{(x_i, y_i, g_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ be the dataset, where x_i is a multi-spectral image patch, y_i its mask, and $g_i \in \{1, \dots, G\}$ the site identifier. Grouped K -fold produces disjoint index sets $\{\mathcal{I}_k^{\text{test}}\}_{k=1}^K$ such that (i) each fold contains whole groups (if i, j share a site, they appear in the *same* fold), and (ii) $\bigcup_k \mathcal{I}_k^{\text{test}} = \{1, \dots, n\}$, $\mathcal{I}_k^{\text{test}} \cap \mathcal{I}_{k'}^{\text{test}} = \emptyset$. For fold k , train on $\mathcal{I}_k^{\text{train}} = \{1, \dots, n\} \setminus \mathcal{I}_k^{\text{test}}$ and evaluate on $\mathcal{I}_k^{\text{test}}$.

For segmentation, we report mean Intersection-over-Union (mIoU) and macro-F1 by averaging per-class scores within each fold and then across folds:

$$\text{mIoU} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=1}^C \frac{\text{TP}_c}{\text{TP}_c + \text{FP}_c + \text{FN}_c}, \quad \text{mF1} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=1}^C \frac{2 \text{TP}_c}{2 \text{TP}_c + \text{FP}_c + \text{FN}_c}. \quad (12)$$

A robust site-grouped splitter akin to GroupKFold was implemented in scikit-learn [6], and is presented in Appendix A.

The grouped cross-validation procedure was implemented in the code using the functions `prepare_dataframe(...)` and `iter_cv_robust(...)`, a lightweight wrapper around grouped data splitting. Five folds ($K=5$) were used with a fixed random seed to ensure reproducibility and identical training hyperparameters across folds. To maintain fairness between resizing regimes (256×256 and 384×384) and model families, class weights were recalculated from the training subset of each fold, and performance metrics were aggregated by the fold mean.

To assess the impact of grouped cross-validation (CV) on model generalisation, model performance was compared under two setups: with CV, where each fold held out an entire site to simulate domain shift, and without CV, where train and validation data were split randomly, increasing the risk of patch-level leakage.

Figure 21 shows the evolution of mean Intersection-over-Union (mIoU) and mean F1-score (mF1) over five training epochs, averaged across all classes.

Figure 21: Comparison of segmentation performance over 5 epochs with and without grouped cross-validation.

Models trained without cross-validation reached higher mIoU and mF1 within the first five epochs, increasing to 0.61 and 0.63, respectively, by epoch five. When grouped CV was applied, mIoU and mF1 peaked lower, at 0.43 and 0.47, providing a more conservative estimate of generalisation under spatial variation.

This difference likely reflects two related mechanisms: random splits permit pixel-level overlap between training and validation patches, which may inflate apparent performance, while grouped cross-validation imposes a greater generalisation demand by requiring the model to perform across spatially distinct regions rather than variations of similar patches seen during training. The results therefore support the use of grouped cross-validation for fair benchmarking on spatially structured data, such as satellite imagery of oil slicks, where temporal or geographic leakage can otherwise inflate reported metrics.

10 Discussion

The aim of this DSG was to evaluate multiple machine-learning approaches for automated detection of oil slicks from shipwrecks using Sentinel-1 SAR and Sentinel-2 optical imagery. The work addressed the limitations of single-image classification by incorporating temporal modelling, multi-modal fusion, and environmental covariates. Experiments showed that model choice alone cannot overcome fundamental data limitations, and that the quality, quantity, and temporal alignment of the available observations remain the primary constraints on performance.

The novel foveated downsampling method reduced SAR image size by a factor of

81 while retaining critical spatial detail around wreck centres, allowing efficient training at fixed input sizes. Spectral analysis of the optical data identified correlated bands and led to composite indices that enhanced contrast between oil films and open water. CNNs outperformed ViTs across most metrics, and bilinear SAR–MSI fusion with gating achieved some accuracy gain.

Environmental covariates such as wind speed, wave height, and temperature were integrated to examine physical influences on slick detectability. Logistic regression and Random Forest baselines linked slick occurrence to calmer sea conditions, while grouped K-fold validation confirmed that spatially independent evaluation is essential for reliable performance estimates. Metadata-based models achieved modest accuracy but captured latent structure that could inform future feature-embedding and fusion frameworks. A physics-informed neural-network concept was also outlined to couple advection–diffusion dynamics with data-driven prediction once concentration estimates become available.

Pixel-level segmentation remained limited by extreme class imbalance, with patch-based methods improving stability but not recall. Future work will focus on semi-supervised and synthetic-data approaches to address sparse labels, improved temporal alignment of weather data, and longer time-series inputs to strengthen temporal reasoning.

This challenge established a reproducible foundation for scalable, multi-modal slick detection and forecasting. Continued development of fusion architectures and physics-aware learning will support operational systems capable of monitoring shipwreck pollution across wider spatial and temporal scales.

10.1 Technical Achievements

This DSG delivered several practical and methodological advances across data processing, model development, and experimental evaluation. A foveated downsampling approach for SAR imagery reduced data volume by a factor of 81 while preserving spatial detail around wreck centres and enabling efficient, reproducible training. Spectral indices and RGB composites derived from Sentinel-2 MSI enhanced contrast between slicks and open water, informing model input selection. Grouped K-fold validation ensured spatially independent performance estimates and prevented leakage between correlated sites.

The modelling experiments spanned a broad configuration space. A total of 36

segmentation configurations were benchmarked across three architectures and two backbones, establishing a baseline for subsequent supervised and semi-supervised development. Temporal models, including 3D CNNs, CNN-LSTMs, and Vision Transformers, showed improved performance when short image sequences were incorporated. Bilinear SAR-MSI fusion with gating achieved a validation accuracy of 93.8 %, confirming the value of multi-sensor integration. Environmental covariates, including wind, wave height, and temperature, showed associations between calm conditions and increased slick visibility. Class-balancing strategies, including weighted and focal loss functions, improved sensitivity to rare slick events without distorting overall class distributions. Metadata-driven approaches using autoencoders and TabTransformers identified latent structure supporting feature embedding and fusion. A physics-informed neural network framework coupling advection-diffusion dynamics with data-driven prediction was also formulated.

10.2 Limitations of Research

Model performance was shaped by several practical and structural constraints inherent in the dataset and available resources. Each presented both a limitation and an opportunity to test mitigation strategies within realistic conditions.

Several limitations affected the scope and performance of the work. A central limitation was class imbalance: slick pixels comprised just 0.08 % of the dataset, constraining all supervised methods. Weighted and focal losses yielded only marginal gains, though balanced sampling and selective inclusion of negative samples improved both recall and model stability. Pixel-level segmentation was also unstable under extreme class imbalance; while patch-based processing improved convergence, it did not fully compensate for the scarcity of positive labels.

Data availability presented further challenges. Only 413 of 6,867 MSI images contained segmentation masks, limiting the diversity of supervised training examples and motivating exploration of semi-supervised, weakly labelled, and synthetic data strategies. Computing restrictions confined several experiments to two or three wreck sites, reducing generalisation and prompting the adoption of grouped K-fold validation, which provided more representative performance estimates.

Sensor and metadata limitations also shaped the experimental design. SAR backscatter from slicks overlapped spectrally with returns from wind-roughened water, producing false positives in radar-only models; multi-sensor fusion with MSI partially mitigated this effect. Weather and sea-state covariates were recorded at three-hour intervals while satellite acquisitions were irregular, precluding direct temporal fusion and requiring window-based aggregation to approximate coincident conditions. Several metadata fields were found to be weakly informative or highly correlated, reducing the predictive power of tabular models and necessitating feature pruning and dimensionality reduction. Finally, time and computational constraints inherent to the DSG limited hyperparameter tuning and prevented full implementation of the physics-informed network framework.

Grouped cross-validation confirmed that site-specific overfitting was common, with models often degrading when evaluated on unseen wrecks. The methods developed to counter these limitations provide a clear direction for future work focused on balanced data design, expanded labelling, and better temporal integration of environmental variables.

10.3 Future Work

Based on the successes and limitations of this DSG, several avenues for future development have been identified. Progress will depend on addressing data scarcity and temporal irregularity rather than further optimisation of existing architectures. Priorities include:

Based on the successes and limitations of this DSG, several directions for further development are identified. Progress is likely to depend more on addressing data scarcity and temporal irregularity than on further optimisation of existing architectures. Key priorities include the application of semi- and weakly supervised learning to exploit the large volume of unlabelled imagery through pseudo-labelling and image-level supervision, and the generation of synthetic data using physics-based oil dispersion or rendering models to augment the limited number of labelled slick examples.

Further work is required to address temporal inconsistency in the data. This includes the development of methods capable of handling irregular time series arising from non-uniform satellite revisit intervals, and the integration of higher-frequency environmental covariates to improve conditioning on wind,

wave, and temperature dynamics. In parallel, physics-informed approaches warrant further investigation, particularly in linking meteorological forcing to observed slick persistence, building on the proposed PINN framework once concentration estimation becomes tractable.

Additional priorities include the expansion of labelled datasets through automated or probabilistic labelling, for example, using thresholds derived from band-level statistics, and the application of domain adaptation and transfer learning to improve cross-site generalisation. Hybrid modelling strategies, including CNN–Transformer architectures and multi-modal fusion pipelines, may offer improved representation of both local texture and global context. Consideration should also be given to lightweight or pruned architectures suitable for cloud or embedded deployment, enabling near-real-time operational monitoring.

The exploratory label correction approach documented in Appendix D represents an early-stage contribution that may warrant further investigation. The Gaussian-based probabilistic method demonstrated feasibility for provisional slick labelling, but systematic evaluation of label quality and downstream model impact has not yet been conducted. Refinement of the threshold criteria, extension to additional wreck sites, and validation against confirmed annotations would be necessary before the approach could be adopted as a reliable data augmentation strategy.

Finally, consistent and physically coherent data augmentation procedures for SAR imagery should also be established as a foundational requirement, ensuring that transformations such as rotations and reflections remain valid for image data, segmentation masks, and associated environmental variables.

11 Team members

David Chandler is a Trainee Clinical Scientist in Clinical Scientific Computing at University College London Hospital. His work focuses on the development and deployment of digital, medical device and AI systems to improve healthcare pathways and patient outcomes. Within the DSG, he coordinated model development streams and ensured documentation and reporting were consistent with agreed requirements

Krishna Chandnani is a master's student pursuing an MPA in Data Science for Public Policy at The London School of Economics and Political Science. She acted as the facilitator of this DSG. She has contributed to band selection and exploratory analysis.

Aditi Goswami is an AI practitioner with over 8+ years of industrial experience in core AI. She has a MSc in AI from University of St Andrews. An MBA student at University of Cambridge. She was mostly involved with analysing the SAR data, data correction and inputs to modelling and data imbalance.

Ryan Marinelli is a postdoctoral researcher affiliated with the Language Technology Group at the University of Oslo. His contributions to the research include the development of a random forest classifier and a temporal 3D convolutional neural network for sequence analysis.

Preben M. Ness is a PhD student at Simula Research Laboratory and The Norwegian University of Science and Technology, specialising in causal neural networks and representation learning. He proposed and implemented the Foveated Downsampling method, implemented, trained, and tested the ViT and Transformer models, and built the associated torch dataloaders.

Brian O'Donovan is a PhD student on the MRC Precision Medicine DTP at the University of Edinburgh, affiliated with the School of Engineering (IDCOM) and The College of Medicine and Veterinary Medicine (IGC). He has contributed to the data processing, visualisation, and time series modelling. .

Harvey Peake is a Mathematician, specialising in applied mathematics and

machine learning development. His work involves the development of AI and ML models for integration into concepts, fusing with sensor systems for real-world applications.

Tom Potter is an Engineer within the AI Research team at BBC Research & Development. His work involves developing and deploying prototype AI and ML models within BBC workflows to help journalists and creators to inform, educate, and entertain. He specialises in ML Engineering, LLMs, and AI provenance.

Imad Ali Shah is affiliated with the Connaught Automotive Research Group, University of Galway, Ireland. His research focuses on multimodal automotive perception. Within DSG, he worked on multispectral data analysis, involving preprocessing, band selection, and perception for slick shape delineation.

Sara Shahin

PhD student in simulation AI-based spatio-temporal biodiversity modelling, Queen Mary University of London. Contributed to oil slick detection by implementing grouped cross-validation, exploratory data analysis, and lightweight model benchmarking for multispectral semantic segmentation.

Krupali Thakur is an InterTradeIreland Project Manager and Applied AI Engineer at Gewardz Health, with an MSc in Artificial Intelligence from Queen's University Belfast. She contributed to this project by developing CNN baselines, balancing datasets to address class imbalance, and analysing model performance against ViTs, with a focus on practical reproducibility and model interpretability.

Chau Thi Thuy Tran is currently pursuing a PhD in Informatics at the University of Oslo (UiO), Norway, with a research focus on emotion recognition using multimodal deep learning models. Her contributes on this DSG is developing sequence-based dataloaders and implementing CNN-LSTM models to capture the spatial and temporal features of data for detecting oil slicks.

Giuseppe Tripodi is a third-year PhD student at the University of Manchester, specialising in transformer-based multimodal models. He contributed metadata analysis, autoencoder and TabTransformer implementations, and transformer-based classification of CNN embeddings.

Aditi Vaidya is a Data Scientist at Natwest Group, focusing on building and deploying AI and ML solutions for the Commercial & Institutional Franchise of the bank. She specialises in Natural Language Processing in the Bank's AI Hub.

Mengxin Xi is a PhD student at King's College London, affiliated with the Statistics Group. She has contributed to the data exploration, and visualisation.

Shizhe (Jay) Xu is a PhD student at the Nuffield Department of Population Health at the University of Oxford, specialising in machine learning-driven

statistical methods for genetic research. His contributions include developing a time-sequence dataloader and data augmentation, designing and training a temporal 3D CNN, visualising the outputs of 3D CNNs and Random Forest models, and constructing a bilinear fusion model to integrate SAR and MSI imagery.

Eric Martin is a Lecturer in Environmental Engineering at the University of Greenwich, specialising in applied hydrogeological engineering. His role in this project was PI: constructing the data challenge, coordinating working groups, discussing ongoing work, and editing the report.

Hayden Close is a challenge owner at Cefas and also PhD student at Plymouth University combining marine imagery and machine learning. He has contributed to the data exploration, visualisation, and providing context and direction within the group.

Evie James is a Marine and Coastal Data Scientist within the Coastal Processes team at Cefas, and was the Challenge Owner, explaining the scientific context of this work and consulting on questions.

Tiago Silva is a Senior Physical Oceanographer at the Centre for Environment, Fisheries and Aquaculture Science (CEFAS) with a PhD from the University of Sheffield. Tiago uses a combination of numerical modelling and satellite observations to study the health of the Oceans and is particularly interested in the interactions between marine organisms and the physical environment. He was the Challenge Owner, explaining the scientific context of this work and consulting on questions.

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Appendix A Algorithm Summaries

Algorithm 1: Construction of Temporal Sequence Dataset from MSI Imagery

Input: Root directory R ; metadata CSV M ; sequence length L .
Output: Dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{(S, W, y)\}$.

```
// --- Load and map labels ---
1 Load metadata  $M$  and map labels  $Y \mapsto 1, N \mapsto 0$ ;
2 Extract timestamps from filenames to build label_map[t] ∈ {0, 1};
// --- Iterate over ship directories ---
3 for each ship directory  $S \in R$  do
4   Collect all TIFF images with timestamps and sort chronologically;
   // --- Form temporal sequences ---
5   for  $i = 1$  to  $N - L + 1$  do
6     Form window  $W = \{I_i, I_{i+1}, \dots, I_{i+L-1}\}$ ;
7     Let  $t_{i+L-1}$  be the timestamp of the last image in  $W$ ;
8     Assign label  $y \leftarrow \text{label\_map}[t_{i+L-1}]$ ;
9     Store sample  $(S, W, y)$  in  $\mathcal{D}$ ;
   // --- Post-processing ---
10 Resize each image to  $(H, W)$  and normalize to  $[0, 1]$ ;
11 Return  $\mathcal{D}$  with each sequence tensor of shape  $(L, C, H, W)$ ;
```

Algorithm 2: Grouped K -fold Train–Validate; Per-Fold Class Weights

Input: Model builder $b(\cdot)$; epochs T ; loss \mathcal{L} (Dice+Focal with weights); AMP flag; metrics {IoU, F1}.

Output: Per-fold metrics and fold-mean summary.

```
1 for  $(k, \mathcal{I}_k^{train}, \mathcal{I}_k^{val})$  do
2    $\mathcal{D}_{tr} \leftarrow \mathcal{D}[\mathcal{I}_k^{train}]; \mathcal{D}_{va} \leftarrow \mathcal{D}[\mathcal{I}_k^{val}];$ 
   // Datasets original resizing regime ( 2562 or 3842)
3   Build loaders  $DL_{tr}, DL_{va}$  (batch size fixed across folds);
   // Per-fold class weights from training masks only
4    $w_k \leftarrow \text{calculate\_class\_weights}(DL_{tr});$ 
   // Fresh model + optimizer + (optional) AMP scaler
5    $f_k \leftarrow b(\text{backbone}, \text{in\_channels}, \text{num\_classes});$ 
6   Initialize AdamW ( $\eta, \lambda$ ); initialize GradScaler if CUDA;
7   for  $t = 1$  to  $T$  do
   // --- Train ---
8   foreach  $(x, y) \in DL_{tr}$  do
9      $\hat{y} \leftarrow f_k(x)$  (AMP autocast if enabled);
10     $L \leftarrow \mathcal{L}(\hat{y}, y; w_k);$ 
11    Backpropagate & optimizer step (scaled if AMP);
   // --- Validate ---
12  Accumulate per-class TP, FP, FN over  $DL_{va}$ ;
13  Compute  $mIoU_k^{(t)}$  and  $mF1_k^{(t)}$ ; apply early stopping on plateau;
14  Record best  $mIoU_k, mF1_k$  (epoch with max mIoU) and save
   checkpoint;
15 Aggregate:  $\overline{mIoU} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_k mIoU_k, ;$ 
16  $\overline{mF1} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_k mF1_k, ;$ 
17 report mean  $\pm$  sd across folds.;
```

1. Extract one row per image with columns `image_path`, `mask_path`, and the site key `site`.
2. List unique sites and shuffle them using a fixed random seed.
3. Greedily assign sites to K bins to balance the number of images per fold, ensuring that entire sites remain in the same fold.
4. For each fold k : *train* on images whose site \notin fold k ; *validate* on images whose site \in fold k .

Appendix B Semantic Performance Metrics

Table 9: Semantic segmentation model performance across 36 configurations for oil slick detection. Best overall performance is underlined; best per modality highlighted in red (model performance) and blue (slick detection).

Input	Size	Model	Backbone	mIoU	mF1	IoU per Class			F1 per Class			
						0	1	2	0	1	2	
Patches	512	DeepLabV3+	EfficientNet-b4	67.42	71.05	98.22	10.11	93.92	99.10	17.49	96.57	
			ResNet50	68.12	72.27	98.37	12.43	93.54	99.18	21.10	96.53	
		PSPNet	EfficientNet-b4	67.84	72.46	97.88	13.27	92.38	98.93	22.54	95.91	
			ResNet50	67.16	71.73	97.60	12.08	91.81	98.78	20.93	95.49	
		UNet	EfficientNet-b4	68.24	72.67	98.28	13.56	92.89	99.13	22.75	96.14	
			ResNet50	67.22	71.48	98.05	11.28	92.34	99.01	19.69	95.73	
	384	DeepLabV3+	EfficientNet-b4	66.47	70.17	98.11	9.19	92.09	99.05	15.86	95.60	
			ResNet50	67.99	71.94	97.44	11.52	95.01	98.70	19.81	97.31	
		PSPNet	EfficientNet-b4	68.21	72.64	97.51	13.73	93.40	98.73	22.82	96.37	
			ResNet50	66.88	71.38	98.04	16.52	86.08	99.01	26.62	88.50	
		UNet	EfficientNet-b4	64.65	69.05	97.82	12.69	83.44	98.89	21.40	86.86	
			ResNet50	65.04	68.45	98.36	10.55	86.22	99.17	17.61	88.58	
256	DeepLabV3+	EfficientNet-b4	66.19	71.17	95.85	13.42	89.31	97.87	22.69	92.94		
		ResNet50	65.82	70.60	96.63	13.35	87.48	98.28	22.06	91.45		
	PSPNet	EfficientNet-b4	66.07	70.87	96.64	14.98	86.60	98.29	24.59	89.74		
		ResNet50	68.84	74.18	96.14	17.51	92.87	98.02	28.49	96.01		
	UNet	EfficientNet-b4	67.61	72.77	96.52	16.51	89.80	98.22	26.80	93.28		
		ResNet50	66.11	71.27	95.83	14.41	88.08	97.87	23.91	92.04		
Average Performance				66.99	71.45	97.41	13.17	90.40	98.68	22.06	93.61	
Resized	512	DeepLabV3+	EfficientNet-b4	65.35	67.31	98.58	2.78	94.69	99.28	5.40	97.24	
			ResNet50	69.19	72.05	99.58	10.07	97.92	99.79	17.40	98.95	
		PSPNet	EfficientNet-b4	67.96	70.38	99.45	7.05	97.36	99.72	12.76	98.66	
			ResNet50	69.16	72.49	99.37	10.96	97.17	99.68	19.21	98.56	
		UNet	EfficientNet-b4	66.41	68.02	99.15	3.15	96.94	99.57	6.06	98.43	
			ResNet50	54.52	59.71	78.07	0.08	85.41	86.98	0.15	91.99	
		384	DeepLabV3+	EfficientNet-b4	66.92	68.61	99.40	4.18	97.17	99.70	7.58	98.56
				ResNet50	68.59	71.21	99.56	8.24	97.96	99.78	14.87	98.97
			PSPNet	EfficientNet-b4	67.11	69.06	99.42	4.80	97.12	99.71	8.94	98.53
				ResNet50	67.63	70.53	99.11	7.90	95.86	99.56	14.15	97.88
			UNet	EfficientNet-b4	67.01	68.75	99.36	4.18	97.51	99.68	7.83	98.73
				ResNet50	57.33	61.49	92.79	0.01	79.20	96.21	0.01	88.26
	256	DeepLabV3+	EfficientNet-b4	66.10	67.68	99.12	2.73	96.45	99.56	5.29	98.18	
			ResNet50	66.19	68.07	98.97	3.75	95.86	99.48	6.87	97.87	
		PSPNet	EfficientNet-b4	65.62	67.14	99.01	2.14	95.70	99.50	4.14	97.79	
			ResNet50	66.71	68.72	99.22	4.55	96.37	99.61	8.40	98.14	
		UNet	EfficientNet-b4	66.93	68.62	99.31	4.12	97.37	99.65	7.55	98.66	
			ResNet50	67.58	69.73	99.39	5.80	97.55	99.69	10.75	98.76	
	Average Performance				65.91	68.31	97.71	4.81	95.20	98.73	8.74	97.62

Appendix C Metadata-Driven Classification

The following documents an exploratory investigation into metadata-driven classification as an alternative to image-based detection. Although results were limited by class imbalance and feature discriminability, the approach confirmed that metadata alone is insufficient for reliable slick detection, motivating its use as a complementary input within multi-modal fusion pipelines rather than as a stand alone modality. Metadata features were independently evaluated for their capacity to predict slick presence. The metadata included acquisition and sensor parameters such as incidence angle, solar irradiance, cloud coverage, and geolocation attributes. Although these variables do not describe the visual content of the imagery, they capture observation conditions and acquisition geometry that may indirectly correlate with slick detectability.

Before training the metadata-based models, a structured preprocessing pipeline was applied to ensure data quality and consistency. Columns containing more than 30% missing values were removed to minimise sparsity effects. Features and labels were then separated, with *Slick_Detected* defined as the binary target variable. Categorical attributes were encoded using label encoding, which was particularly relevant for parameters such as incidence angle and solar irradiance across spectral bands, where overlapping or ordinal relationships could influence model interpretability.

Metadata fields, including product identifiers, spacecraft names, and timestamps, were excluded to prevent model bias and redundancy. The cleaned and standardised dataset was then stored for subsequent modelling experiments.

Methods

To evaluate whether latent patterns within the metadata carried discriminative information for slick detection, an autoencoder-based representation learning approach was implemented.

The autoencoder was implemented as a fully connected feed-forward network operating directly on the tabular metadata. The encoder sequentially reduced feature dimensionality through layers of 128, 64, and 32 neurons, each employing ReLU activation. The decoder mirrored this structure, reconstructing the original feature space from the latent representation to ensure information retention and stable convergence.

To address class imbalance, a weighted reconstruction loss was employed, increasing the penalty for reconstruction errors in the minority (slick) class. However, this adjustment did not produce the anticipated improvement in representation quality. The extreme imbalance between classes persisted as a dominant limitation, with the minority class remaining too under-represented for robust characterisation. As demonstrated in the results section, the combined effects of imbalance and limited feature discriminability constrained the overall performance of the autoencoder-based approach.

After training, the decoder was discarded, and the encoder was retained as a feature extractor to transform raw metadata into low-dimensional latent embeddings. These compressed representations were subsequently used as input to a class-balanced logistic regression model, selected to evaluate whether a simple linear classifier could achieve meaningful discrimination when supported by non-linear feature transformations.

This two-stage pipeline enabled evaluation of the hypothesis that metadata, though noisy and partially redundant, contains structured information that can be disentangled through representation learning. By comparing classification performance in the latent space with that obtained from raw features, the contribution of unsupervised feature extraction to slick detection was quantitatively assessed.

The preprocessing pipeline followed the same structure as in the autoencoder experiment, incorporating label encoding for categorical attributes, standardisation of numerical features, and encoding of the binary target variable. To address the pronounced class imbalance, class weights derived from the training split were integrated into the loss function. Stratified train–validation–test partitioning was applied to preserve proportional representation of the minority class across all subsets.

The objective of this approach was to determine whether a transformer-based tabular model could surpass simpler architectures in handling mixed-type metadata, and to evaluate whether the attention mechanism could reveal informative feature interactions contributing to reliable slick detection.

Training and Outputs

The training behaviour of the autoencoder, illustrated in Figure 22a, exhibited rapid convergence, with reconstruction loss approaching zero within a few epochs.

However, it is important to note that training was conducted exclusively on normal (non-slick) samples, without explicit inclusion of anomalous cases.

The underlying objective was to train the model to characterise normal samples such that, when an anomalous instance is encoded into the latent space, its representation would deviate substantially from the embedding distribution of normal samples.

The training curve of the logistic regression model, shown in Figure 22b, demonstrates rapid convergence when trained on embeddings produced by the pre-trained encoder. The training loss decreased quickly, while the validation loss exhibited a gradual increase, indicating a pronounced tendency toward overfitting.

(a) Logistic regressor training and validation loss

(b) Autoencoder training and validation loss

Figure 22: Training and validation loss curves for (a) the logistic regressor trained on embeddings from the pre-trained encoder and (b) the autoencoder trained on positive samples only.

Evaluation of the autoencoder on the raw test outputs revealed a complete failure to identify Class 0, with both recall and F1 score equal to zero, indicating severe prediction imbalance. Fine-tuning improved performance substantially for Class 0, achieving precision and F1 scores of 0.97 and 0.77, respectively, although Class 1 remained poorly represented with an F1 score of 0.23. The overall accuracy increased to 0.65, suggesting partial improvement but continued bias toward the majority class. .

Table 10: Final evaluation metrics for the autoencoder and logistic regressor models on the test set.

Model	Class 0			Class 1			Acc.	Macro F1
	Prec.	Rec.	F1	Prec.	Rec.	F1		
Autoencoder	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.07
Logistic Regressor	0.97	0.64	0.77	0.14	0.77	0.23	0.65	0.50

Appendix D Exploratory Label Correction for Unlabelled SAR Imagery

The following documents an exploratory investigation into automated label correction for SAR imagery lacking segmentation masks. Given that only 413 of 6,867 images contained annotations, a method was developed to identify probable slick pixels in unlabelled images using spectral statistics derived from confirmed slick examples. The analysis was conducted on the Canberra wreck and represents a preliminary approach that warrants more rigorous evaluation in future work.

Feature Engineering

The wreck metadata file was extended with additional features derived from the imagery. For images containing segmentation masks, slick area was computed by counting pixels with a mask value of 1, and recorded in a dedicated column.

Band-level statistics were subsequently extracted for all three spectral bands. A cropped region encompassing the full spatial extent of slicks associated with the wreck was defined, and pixel values within this region were recorded for each image. The minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation were computed per band, yielding twelve additional features: B1_min, B1_max, B1_mean, B1_std, B2_min, B2_max, B2_mean, B2_std, B3_min, B3_max, B3_mean, and B3_std.

Statistical Analysis and Label Inconsistency

The metadata was partitioned into two subsets: images with confirmed slick labels (DF1) and images labelled as no-slick (DF2). Band statistics were compared across the two subsets to assess separability. For B1_std, DF1 exhibited a range of 2.76 to 6.68, while DF2 spanned 1.94 to 15.36. Given that no-slick images should contain only open water, the elevated upper range in DF2 suggests either undetected slicks in the unlabelled subset or that band statistics alone are insufficient to reliably discriminate slick from non-slick conditions.

Probabilistic Label Correction

A Gaussian-based approach was developed to assign provisional labels to unlabelled images. For each image with a confirmed mask, the pixel coordinates

of slick regions were identified and the corresponding SAR values extracted for all three bands. A Gaussian distribution was fitted to each band, and its mean and standard deviation retained as reference parameters. A bounding box was defined to represent the full spatial extent of slicks across the wreck.

For each unlabelled image, a per-pixel z-score was computed against the fitted Gaussian for each band. Pixels where the z-score fell below 1 across all three bands were classified as probable slick pixels. Images in which fewer than 1,000 pixels met this criterion were assigned a no-slick label; those exceeding this threshold were provisionally labelled as containing a slick. This approach represents a preliminary proof of concept; systematic evaluation of label quality and downstream model impact remains an avenue for future work.

It should be noted, however, that reliance on band-level standard deviation as the primary discriminative feature risks conflating genuine slick pixels with high-variance noise sources inherent to SAR imagery, including speckle and surface roughness effects. This limitation underlies the need for more rigorous validation before the approach can be considered reliable.

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